

CEOS_SE - Citizen-Enhanced Open Science in Southeastern Europe Higher Education Knowledge Hubs - Initial DMP- V.2

1. Data summary

Provide a summary of the data addressing the following issues:

- State the purpose of the data collection/generation
- Explain the relation to the objectives of the project
- Specify the types and formats of data generated/collected
- Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)
- Specify the origin of the data
- State the expected size of the data (if known)
- Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful

The aim of the project is to raise awareness and mainstream practices in SE European countries (BG, CY, EL, HR, IT, RS), that perform less well in Open Science (OS) and Citizen Science (CS) and have low awareness on/involvement in major developments, such as the ones related to the EOSC, as well as to monitor performance and processes in OS/CS implementation, document and publicly share best practices in a FAIR way, and engage non-expert groups of the public in social participation and collaboration.

CEOS_SE keywords are upskilling, awareness-raising, best practice sharing, and citizen engagement. Training will be carried out from a train-the-trainers perspective. Hence, the approach would be the widest possible openness for any data stemming from the project.

Data reuse by other libraries, researchers, associations and citizens is an implicit target of the project. For this purpose,

- a Community CEOS_SE has been created in Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/ceos_se/

- the project website section Results will display all the relevant material:

<http://ceosse-project.eu/the-results/>

Data collection includes interviews and surveys to listen to the community and better tailor guidelines and training material to its needs. For GDPR-related issues, a consent form has been signed by the interviewees.

CEOS_SE will mainly deal with textual data, as detailed in Table 1:

Category of data	Type	Format (ongoing)	Format (preservation)	Expected size	Open/Closed	Licence
A. Textual	A1. Reports	.doc	.pdf	1 G	Open	CC BY
	A2. Guidelines	.doc	.pdf	1 G	Open	CC BY
	A3. Training material	.ppt	.pdf	10 G	Open	CC BY
	A4. Consent form	.doc	.pdf	10 M	Open	CC BY
B. Tabellar	B1. Survey results	.xls	.csv	1 G	Open	CC BY
C. Images	C1. Video recordings/conferences and training courses	.mp4	.mp4	30 G	Open	CC BY
	C2. Video recordings/interviews	.mp4	.mp4	30 G	Restricted - access upon non disclosure agreement	CC BY
	C3. Photos taken during events	.jpeg	.jpg	15 G	Open	CC BY

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

- Outline the discoverability of data (metadata provision)
- Outline the identifiability of data and refer to standard identification mechanism. Do you make use of persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers?
- Outline naming conventions used
- Outline the approach towards search keyword
- Outline the approach for clear versioning
- Specify standards for metadata creation (if any). If there are no standards in your discipline describe what metadata will be created and how

CEOS_SE material deposited in Zenodo will get a DOI and will be Findable via the Zenodo metadata schema. All the partners share a Google Drive folder, structured as follows:

level1	level 2	level 3
CEOS partners	Background readings	
	Visual guidelines	EU branding requirements
		Project branding and logos
		Templates
	Preparation Phase	Letter of Support
		CEOS proposal
		Grant Agreement and annexes
		Erasmus+ programme guide
		Pre-kick off meeting
		Kick off meeting
		One pagers and CEOS presentation
	Implementation	PR 1
		PR2
		PR3
		PR4
		PR5
		PR6
		Engagement and outreach
		Coordination
		Transnational meeting and LTTA
		Quality assurance
		Advisory board
		Final deliverables

A file naming schema will be provided. Versioning is clearly marked on the files simply by numbering (_V1, _V2.1...). Zenodo takes care of versioning preserving all the versions of uploaded files and assigning each a DOI.

2.2 Making data openly accessible:

- **Specify which data will be made openly available? If some data is kept closed provide rationale for doing so**
- **Specify how the data will be made available**
- **Specify what methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**
- **Specify where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited**
- **Specify how access will be provided in case there are any restrictions**

CEOS_SE material will be available via

- a Community CEOS_SE has been created in Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/communities/ceos_se/

- the project website:

<http://ceosse-project.eu/>

The material will be openly accessible with the exception of:

- signed consent forms, which will be deposited in the UPatras space of the

HARDMIN data repository (<https://hardmin.heal-link.gr>)

- interviews recordings with participants to Focus groups according to the interviewees options.

Preservation formats will be open formats like .pdf or .csv, as stated in Table 1.

2.3 Making data interoperable:

- **Assess the interoperability of your data. Specify what data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies you will follow to facilitate interoperability.**
- **Specify whether you will be using standard vocabulary for all data types present in your data set, to allow interdisciplinary interoperability? If not, will you provide mapping to more commonly used ontologies?**

Producing mainly textual documents, interoperability is ensured by using open formats whenever possible.

2.4 Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

- **Specify how the data will be licenced to permit the widest reuse possible**
- **Specify when the data will be made available for re-use. If applicable, specify why and for what period a data embargo is needed**
- **Specify whether the data produced and/or used in the project is useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why**
- **Describe data quality assurance processes**
- **Specify the length of time for which the data will remain re-usable**

The default licence for CEOS_SE material is CC BY (Creative Commons Attribution).

Reuse by librarians, researchers, and citizens is one of the aims of the project, hence all the material will be available as soon as produced, with the exceptions stated in section 2.2 (consent forms and some interviews recordings).

The material will be deposited in Zenodo and will be indefinitely available.

Zenodo ensures files integrity via checksum checks and a quality assurance process (see <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>).

3. Allocation of resources

Explain the allocation of resources, addressing the following issues:

- **Estimate the costs for making your data FAIR. Describe how you intend to cover these costs**
- **Clearly identify responsibilities for data management in your project**
- **Describe costs and potential value of long term preservation**

Responsible for the Data Management Plan is Elena Giglia (University of Turin), assisted by Andrej Vrcon (CEOS_SE Project Manager). Due to the low volume of data generated, no additional costs are foreseen.

The website is powered and maintained by LIBER at <https://ceosse-project.eu/>.

Each partner has the responsibility to manage and share its own produced material, according to the common rules set in this DMP.

4. Data security

Address data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data

CEOS_SE deals with no sensitive data except for consent forms, which will be safely stored in the UPatras space of their HARDMIN data repository.

Each partner will provide a data backup according to its own institution's rules and policies.

5. Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables. Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former

Not applicable.

6. Other

Refer to other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management that you are using (if any)

As per participants data, special conditions in section **I6 of the Grant Agreement**, namely

I.6.1 Data controller

The entity acting as a data controller as provided for in Article II.7, the data controller: is

Head of Unit B4

Directorate B – Youth, Education & Erasmus+

Directorate-General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture

European Commission

B-1049 Brussels

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